

GOOGLE MEET MEDIA-ASSISTED METHOD OF LEARNING: ITS EFFECT ON LEARNERS' MATHEMATICAL PERFORMANCE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 10

Pages: 1312-1318

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2235

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13353954

Manuscript Accepted: 07-20-2024

Google Meet Media-Assisted Method of Learning: Its Effect on Learners' Mathematical Performance

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Abstract

This action research aimed to evaluate the impact of the Google Meet Media-Assisted Lecture Method on the academic performance of Grade Six learners in Mathematics. Due to the shift away from traditional face-to-face instruction, MathPACKS modules were delivered exclusively through the Google Meet online platform. The study focused on assessing students' performance levels before and after exposure to this method. Participants included 30 identified Grade six learners from Alimodian Central Elementary School during the 2021-2022 academic year. The research employed a One Group Pretest-Posttest Design to measure performance changes, with the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test used to determine statistical significance. Results indicated that prior to exposure to the Google Meet Media-Assisted Lecture Method, students displayed an average level of performance. However, following the implementation of the method, their performance significantly improved, achieving higher academic outcomes in Mathematics. These findings underscore the method's effectiveness in enhancing students' proficiency in the subject. The study suggests that integrating the Google Meet Media-Assisted Lecture Method into educational practices can yield positive results in Mathematics education for Grade six students. By utilizing online platforms for instructional delivery, educators can potentially optimize learning experiences and elevate academic achievements. This research contributes valuable insights into innovative teaching strategies that leverage digital tools to improve educational outcomes in contemporary educational contexts.

Keywords: *Google Meet Media-Assisted Lecture Method, MathPACKS modules, action research*

Introduction

Teaching and learning math in the new normal is tough and truly challenging. There will be uncertainties, anxieties, and fears. Misconceptions may arise, and hatred for the subject or the teacher may arise. Math teachers might fail to develop the students toward the twin goals of K-12 Math – critical thinking and problem-solving. Even if a solution to a math problem is well-presented in a module, textbook or learning activity sheet, it will be less effective. Math teachers just don't teach true or false, $1 + 2$ and $x \& y$, they need to explain various processes systematically for learners to understand both concept and content (Saladino, 2020).

Now, the Department of Education (DepEd) has sought to minimize or totally forego face-to-face teaching and opt for blended learning through modules, television, radio, and online to prevent the spread of the virus and protect school children among the most vulnerable during this period. While this problem encompasses the teaching of all subjects in basic education, secondary education, and even college, perhaps, there is no greater challenge among subject teachers compared to the challenge that math teachers must face (Dela Cruz, 2020).

According to Caudill (2020) Aside from the fear of students getting sick, the lack of physical interaction between students and teachers drove her interviewees to tears. No matter what they do, the current situation is detrimental to providing students with the best practices for their education.

Teachers feel helpless in providing students with what they truly need. The question of how to motivate learners to be interested and involved in math has become a leading concern for math teachers during this time of the COVID-19 pandemic. This is true for the learners of Alimodian Central Elementary School. Learners are struggling with their lessons, especially in Mathematics. Only 76 Out of 114 incoming grade 6 learners, which is 67% of their enrollment, got 80% and above mastery level based on their final grade in Mathematics for S.Y. 2020 - 2021. They have difficulties in grasping and understanding the information provided in the printed modules given by their teacher if no one is helping them.

Recent trends in education show that digital platforms are playing a vital role in enhancing teaching, learning, and research. In Mathematics Education, many mathematicians acknowledge the value and importance of a Blended Learning (BL) approach in teaching mathematics, taking advantage of the different mathematical software that can be used in teaching. Blended Learning is a teaching methodology that makes use of technology (online resources, videos, software) on top of the face-to-face classroom contact between teachers and students (Bhatti et al., 2016).

Synchronous Teaching and learning is one of the methods used in teaching online through Blended Learning. According to Mathproject (2020) Synchronous learning allows the student to experience the dynamic benefits of in-class learning: engagement and instructional depth from real-time interaction. Through this method of learning, the student can engage in active and face-to-face discussions, allowing them to explore and understand topics from different perspectives. This learning also provides instant feedback, as students can ask questions during the lesson and receive guidance from their teacher. With this exchange of knowledge and depth of discussion, synchronous learning provides a human element that helps students feel motivated and engaged when transitioning to online learning.

The methods of synchronous online learning include video conferencing, teleconferencing, live chatting, and live-streaming lectures.

One of the applications that can be used to facilitate Synchronous learning is Google Meet. Google Meet is a video conferencing service from Google. It's a great solution for both individuals and businesses to meet on audio and video calls. It was born from Google Hangouts but boasts some unique features. Google Meet is available on the web and on phones and tablets for Android and iOS (Keeley, 2020). According to Google.com, Schools or organizations can use Google Meet with staff and students for video meetings. When teachers use Meet for distance learning, they can Start and join video meetings in the Classroom using a dedicated link for their classes, use moderation participation, get attendance reports, start a video meeting from Gmail, and control access to video meetings.

The new interactive approach through the media application, Google Meet makes new knowledge and experience different both by educators and students. Different knowledge and experience are gained through new interactive approaches (Borges & Mello-Carpes, 2015). Students study at home through applications agreed upon by educators and students. The learning room component that was originally a classroom in the school environment has shifted to the Google Meet application room (Roscoe, 2014).

According to Setyawan et al. (2020), the lecture method using the media help of the Google Meet group is more effective than WhatsApp groups and Schoology groups in terms of building knowledge. The learning process through Google Meet involves audio and visual aspects where the lecturer delivers the material directly through the media. The students and lecturers communicate with each other about the material and ask questions about what is not yet understood and can be heard directly by other students so that the process of building student knowledge is higher than Whatsapp and Schoology groups.

The rising popularity of this method of study has resulted in an extraordinary boom in the industry. Studies show an annual growth of 5% or more in the online learning space, year on year. Learning online helps improve digital literacy as it provides students with an insight into how to be effective online and communicate with content, peers and lecturers (Digitalmarketinginstitute, 2018).

If this method can work well among the learners in terms of their ability to perform in Mathematics, then this strategy can be worth implementing in elementary school where learners have available gadgets and internet connections are available. Whether it is effective or not, it can provide new insights for teachers to consider.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the effect of Google Meet Media-Assisted Lecture Method on the performance in Mathematics of Grade Six Learners on Ratio and Proportion of Alimodian Central Elementary School for School Year 2021 – 2022. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the Mathematical performance of the Grade Six learners before exposure to Google Meet media-assisted lecture method?
2. What is the Mathematical performance of the Grade Six learners after exposure to Google Meet media-assisted lecture method?
3. Is there a significant improvement in the Mathematical performance of the Grade Six learners' before and after exposure to Google Meet media-assisted lecture method?
4. What action should be taken after the conduct of the study?

Literature Review

Google meet is an interactive and alternative media used for online learning. Google Meet assist Educators use the lecture method in indirect learning activities. Interactive learning is expected to help students in building knowledge and learning outcomes (Roscoe, 2014).

Lecture is a method commonly used by educators in learning activities to build student knowledge and learning outcomes. Learning activities require direct communication between educators and students so that the transfer of knowledge in building knowledge and learning outcomes can be well-formed so that the character of students can be directed through the guidance of educators (Barreyro et al., 2019).

The combination of Google Meet's media-assisted lecture methods creates a unique learning experience to achieve learning goals such as building knowledge and student learning outcomes while learning from home. Online media helps students to find information in supporting learning objectives (Lawson, 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a one-group experimental pretest-posttest design. According to Devin Kowalczyk (2020), the reason you run a pretest-posttest experiment is to see if your manipulation, the thing you're looking at, has caused a change in the participants. Since everyone is being manipulated in the same way, any changes you see across the group of participants is likely from the manipulation. This means you test them before experimenting, then you run your experimental manipulation, and then you test them again to see if

there are any changes.

According to Jennings (1988), the one-group pretest and posttest design is an experimental research design where there is only one group of samples. The pretest is given before the intervention, while the posttest, which is the same as the pretest, is given among the respondents after the intervention. After this, the results of the pretest and posttest are compared for the analysis.

Participants

The participants of this study were 30 identified Grade Six learners enrolled in Alimodian Central Elementary School for the school year 2021-2022. Out of the 30 learners, 15 are boys and 15 are girls. Purposive sampling was used to identify the participants. They were chosen based on the availability of the gadgets and internet connectivity needed in the study.

Procedure

Prior to the actual administration of the study, permission was secured from the principal of Alimodian Central Elementary School to conduct the action research and was administered to the thirty (30) identified Grade Six learners.

To gather data from the respondents, the researcher constructed a 25-item multiple choice researcher-made test on four (4) MELCs-based competencies on ratio and proportion. The test items were prepared based on a table of specifications considering the levels of behavioral objectives. It was validated by the panel of validators composed of one Master Teacher in Mathematics, one Master Teacher in English for grammar check and one Research Teacher in the District of Alimodian I.

A pretest was conducted as a primary learners' performance. The validated researcher-made test was given to parents/guardians during the distribution of modules and learners will answer it at home. After the learner done answering the pretest, the parent/guardian returned it following the schedule of the module retrieval. The researcher gathered, checked and scored the papers after receiving it. Pretest mean scores were computed to determine the level of performance of Grade Six learners prior to intervention.

As an intervention, learners underwent Google Meeting sessions twice a week, every Tuesday and Thursday that will last for 60 minutes each session from 9:00 AM – 10:00 AM, for four (4) consecutive weeks to assist them in answering their modules thru Lecture Method. In the conduct of this research, the participants utilized the Division Initiated MathPACKS Module which underwent series of validation and quality assurance from Learning Resource Personnel of the Schools Division of Iloilo.

After the intervention, equivalent posttest was administered to the learners. Posttest mean score was computed to determine the level of performance of Grade Six learners after the intervention has been made.

After the tests, the researcher gathered, checked, scored, analyzed and interpreted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

The performance of the respondents was determined through a 25-item researcher-made multiple-choice type of test. The mathematical skills were based on the mean scores of the learners. A five-point scale was used to describe the mean of the scores of the learners.

<i>Range of Scores</i>	<i>Description</i>
20.01 – 25.00	Very High
15.01 – 20.00	High
10.01 – 15.00	Average
5.01 – 10.00	Low
0.00 – 5.00	Very Low

The range of the mean scores with corresponding description was constructed as basis of analyzing the level of Mathematical performance of the Grade Six learners' after exposure to Google Meet Media-Assisted Lecture Method.

To determine the scale, the lowest score (0) was subtracted from the highest score (25). The result will be divided into 5 giving the quotient of 5. It was then considered as the interval in the scale. The scale is the value between the first category and the next category. This was used as the basis in interpreting the scores.

Data Analysis

The data gathered was subjected to appropriate descriptive and inferential statistics using computerized processing which is the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 software.

The following statistical tools was utilized in interpreting the results of the study.

Mean. This is the weighted mean scores and the mean gain scores of certain variables. This was used to determine the mathematical performance of the participants.

According to Sagepub (n.d.) Mean or arithmetic mean (X or M) is the sum of the scores in a distribution divided by the number of scores in the distribution. It is the most commonly used measure of central tendency. It is often reported with its companion statistic, the standard deviation, which shows how far things vary from the average.

Standard deviation. This was used to determine the respondents' homogeneity or heterogeneity of their mathematical performance.

According to Sagepub (n.d.) Standard deviation (SD) is the most stable measure of variability, it takes into account each and every score in a normal distribution. This descriptive statistic assesses how far individual scores vary in standard unit lengths from its midpoint of 0. For all normal distributions, 95% of the area is within 1.96 standard deviations of the mean.

According to Vedantu (n.d.) Standard Deviation is the measure of the dispersion of data from its mean. It measures the absolute variability of a distribution. The higher is the dispersion or variability of data, the larger will be the standard deviation and the larger will be the magnitude of the deviation of value from the mean whereas the lower is the dispersion or variability of data, the lower will be the standard deviation and the lower will be the magnitude of the deviation of value from the mean. The standard deviation formula is used to find the values of a specific data that is dispersed from the mean value. It is important to observe that the value of standard deviation can never be negative.

Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test. This was utilized to determine the significance of the difference of the mean gain scores of the pre-test and post-test of the learners who were exposed to Google Meet Media-Assisted Method. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

According to Sagepub (n.d.) Wilcoxon sign rank test (W^+) is a nonparametric statistical hypothesis test for the case of two related samples or repeated measurements on a single sample. It can be used as an alternative to the paired Student's t -test when the population cannot be assumed to be normally distributed.

According to Laerd Statistics (n.d.) the Wilcoxon signed-rank test determines whether there is a statistically significant difference in the median of a dependent variable between two related groups. It is the nonparametric equivalent to the paired t -test. As the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test does not assume normality of the differences of the two related groups, it can be used when this assumption has been violated and the use of the paired t -test is inappropriate.

Ethical Considerations

The study is upholding highest ethical standard. Permission to school authorities was secured prior to the conduct of the study. Consent has also been secured from the parents of the participants. Correct and appropriate citations of all sources of data/information utilized in the study will be observed to give due credits to the real author of the said information. On top of this, is the adherence to the anti-plagiarism law.

The data gathered in this study was considered highly confidential and this will not affect the student academic standing. As stipulated in Section 2 of R.A. 10173, that it is the policy of the state to protect the fundamental human right of privacy. Moreover, the provision in Section 8 says that the commission shall always ensure the confidentiality of any personal information that comes to its knowledge and possession.

The researcher properly cited all citations of scholarly articles and related research used and reflected the source in the reference part of this study.

To remain complaint with protocols set by the Inter Agency Task Force with primary objective which is to preserve and protect everybody in this pandemic time, the research will strictly follow all the guidelines.

Results and Discussion

The gathered data were presented in tabular and textual form. The presentation of the data is in accordance with the specific questions in the statement of the problem.

Mathematical performance of the Grade Six learners before exposure to Google Meet media-assisted lecture method

Before the Google Meet media-assisted lecture method was conducted, the data-gathering instrument was administered as a pretest to the respondents. Result in Table 1 revealed that the mathematical performance of grade six was average, that is ($M=14.5667$) before they were exposed to Google Meet media-assisted lecture method.

This was supported by the study of Kuhfeld et al. (2022), that the cumulative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on students' academic achievement has been large. They had tracked changes in math and reading test scores across the first two years of the pandemic and the result is very alarming.

Table 1. *Pretest Mean result of the mathematical performance of the grade six learners' before exposure to Google Meet media-assisted lecture method*

	<i>N</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>Description</i>
Pretest	30	4.48510	14.5667	15	Average

Note: 0-5 - very low, 5.1-10 - low, 10.1-15 - average, 15.1-20 - high, 20.1-25 - very high

Mathematical performance of the Grade Six learners after exposure to Google Meet media-assisted lecture method

After conducting the Google Meet media-assisted lecture method twice a week for 4 weeks, a posttest was given to the respondents of

the study. Table 2 revealed that the mathematical performance of grade six was high ($M=18.4333$) after exposure to Google Meet media-assisted lecture method. There was an increase in the mean score of 3.8666.

Based on research that was done by Setyawan et al. (2020), there are several findings related to the application of the Google Meet media-assisted lecture method while studying at home to build student knowledge and learning outcomes. They added that more effective improvement in learning outcomes in the lecture method using the media helps Google Meet because in the learning process, the delivery of information can be done more optimally.

Table 2. *Posttest Mean result of the mathematical performance of the grade six learners after exposure to Google Meet media-assisted lecture method*

	<i>N</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>Description</i>
Posttest	30	3.68298	18.433	19	High

Note: 0-5 - very low, 5.1-10 - low, 10.1-15 - average, 15.1-20 - high, 20.1-25 - very high

Difference in the Mathematical Performance of the Grade Six learners Before and After exposure to Google Meet Media-Assisted Lecture Method

Pretest and posttest results of the subjects were compared to determine the difference in the level of performance of Grade six learners in Mathematics. Table 3 presents the Wilcoxon signed-rank test on the difference in the level of Mathematical performance of Grade six learners' before and after the exposure in Google Meet media-assisted lecture method ($Mdn=19$, $z = -4.221$, $p < .000$). The result shows that Google Meet media-assisted lecture method significantly improves the level of performance of Grade six learners in Mathematics.

The study of Setyawan et al. (2020) discovered that methods of lecture assisted by Google Meet has a significant influence on the building knowledge and learning outcomes of elementary school teacher education students from the University of Trunojoyo Madura. Also, through this application, student discipline attitudes can be trained. It is necessary to improve learning with support applications that can help teachers and students stand out directly through the network (web), such as Google Meet.

Table 3. *Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test Results on the level of mathematical performance of the grade six learners' before and after exposure to Google Meet media-assisted lecture method*

		<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>	<i>Sum of Ranks</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Posttest - Pretest	Negative Ranks	3a	6.00	18.00	-4.221b	.000	Significant
	Positive Ranks	25b	15.52	388.00			
	Ties	2o					
	Total	30					

Note: $p = .05$ level of significance

Conclusions

Based on the aforementioned findings, the following conclusions were drawn: The Google Meet Media-Assisted lecture method had a great impact on students learning Mathematics, especially during the time of the pandemic. The grade six learners' level of performance in Mathematics was improved after exposure to the Google Meet Media-Assisted lecture method.

Learners showed a significant improvement in their performance in Mathematics after exposure to the Google Meet Media-Assisted lecture method. This implied, Google Meet is an effective online learning platform used in blended learning because learners are provided the opportunities to learn their lessons in Mathematics with the help of their teacher.

Utilizing Google Meet Assisted-Media lecture method as an online learning platform was effective in improving learners' performance in Mathematics. Although they can only be seen in visual and audio form, with this strategy, gaps and difficulties in learning the subject are addressed with the help of the teacher.

It certainly changes the mindset of the teachers in education that the learning process or activity should not always have to be carried out in the class. Therefore, the use of online learning platforms like Google Meet is not only done when there is a pandemic, but also as a new learning style in achieving learning objectives in the future.

In the light of the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are presented: This study proved that Google Meet Media-Assisted Instruction is an effective alternative delivery mode. Therefore, the teachers should use Google Meet online learning platform to improve the performance of the learners in Mathematics especially during blended learning.

Google Meet Media Assisted lecture method is one of a new technique in the new normal educational system, therefore, teachers should be provided training in different online learning platforms and educational learning application for Mathematics learning to be interactive and engaging especially during blended learning.

Learners on the other hand, must be encouraged to improve their study habit especially in Mathematics and be updated to the new trends in technology to improve their performance in the subject.

Parents should cooperate with the school in providing supportive environment at home that will greatly help their children develop good study habits and be motivated more to learn and love Mathematics.

The school administrators may promote and include the use of Google Meet Media Assisted Instruction in learning as one effective strategies in improving learner's performance not only in Mathematics but in all learning areas as well.

Similar investigation may be conducted by future researchers on the other groups of learners so as to confirm the findings that Google Meet Media-Assisted Instruction is an effective strategy to help improve learners level of performance in Mathematics.

Reflection

Due to the emergence of COVID-19 in the Philippines, a lot of changes happened in the educational landscape. One of these is the mode of instruction that was implemented by the Department of Education. The current COVID-19 crisis has obliged most education systems to adopt alternatives to face-to-face teaching and learning. Many education systems moved activities online, to allow instruction to continue despite school closures (OECD, 2020).

Online learning, especially the integration of Google Meet as the medium of instruction, has aided the pursuit of educational attainment towards the learners amid the pandemic. This learning strategy is very beneficial to the learners, teachers, and parents.

Based on a twice a week in four weeks period observation of the grade six class, learners were more enthusiastic and always looked forward to their next math class, expecting another day of learning and understanding their modules hence, it is difficult for them to understand and answer their modules by themselves without the help of their parents or learning facilitators. We cannot go away with the fact that some parents are busy because of work trying to make ends meet, and some have not gone to college because of poverty. Without another more knowledgeable person who can explain complicated concepts in Mathematics, the learners will definitely have difficulty absorbing their lessons. Therefore, with the help of Google Meet Media-Assisted Instruction learners can understand their Mathematics lessons, gaps and difficulties in learning the subject are addressed with the help of the teacher.

At the end of the study, most students were even asking for more Google Class Sessions. Further, based on the impromptu interview to one of the learners, he mentioned, "daad ma'am pirme lang may online class sa math kay para indi ako mabudlayan mag intindi ka module. Nabudlayan daan si nanay mag intindi gani indi na ako ma tudluan"

Though initially, both teachers and learners benefited from this learning strategy, there are some problems that were encountered during the implementation such as internet network and connectivity issues, problems accessing the platform and managing learners' behavior. Nevertheless, based on the findings of the study, Google Meet Media-Assisted lecture method was proven effective educational strategy in improving the level of performance of the learners in Mathematics and continuing learning at home especially during blended learning.

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